

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 115

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 115

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 115:1 "Not to us, O LORD, not to us, But ^bto Your name give glory Because of Your lovingkindness, because of Your ¹truth. ² "Why should the nations say, "Where, now, is their God?" ³ But our "God is in the heavens; He ^bdoes whatever He pleases. ⁴ Their "idols are silver and gold, The ^bwork of man's hands. ⁵ They have mouths, but they "cannot speak; They have eyes, but they cannot see; ⁶ They have ears, but they cannot hear; They have noses, but they cannot smell; ⁷ ¹They have hands, but they cannot feel; ²They have feet, but they cannot walk; They cannot make a sound with their throat. ⁸ "Those who make them ¹will become like them, Everyone who trusts in them.</p>	<p>Psa. 115:1 לֹא לָנוּ יְהוָה לֹא לָנוּ כִּי- לְשִׁמְךָ תִּתֵּן כְּבוֹד עַל-חַסְדֶּיךָ עַל- אֲמִתְּךָ : 2 לְמַחַי יֵאמְרוּ הַגּוֹיִם אֵי- זָא אֱלֹהֵיהֶם : 3 וְאֵלֵהֵינוּ בַשָּׁמַיִם כֹּל אֲשֶׁר-חַפֵּץ עָשָׂה : 4 עַצְבֵיהֶם כֶּסֶף וְזָהָב מַעֲשֵׂה יַדֵי אָדָם : 5 פֶּה- לָהֶם וְלֹא יִדְבְּרוּ עֵינַיִם לָהֶם וְלֹא יִרְאוּ : 6 אָזְנוֹתַי לָהֶם וְלֹא יִשְׁמְעוּ אָף לָהֶם וְלֹא יִרְיָחוּן : 7 יְדֵיהֶם וְלֹא יַמְשִׁיחוּן רַגְלֵיהֶם וְלֹא יִהְלְכוּ לֹא-יִהְיוּ בְגִדוֹנָם : 8 כַּמּוֹהֶם יִתְּנוּ עֲשִׂיהֶם כֹּל אֲשֶׁר-בָּטַח בָּהֶם : 9 יִשְׂרָאֵל בָּטַח בִּיהוָה עֲזָרָם וּמְגִנָּתָם הוּא : 10 בַּיִת אֲהָרֹן בָּטְחוּ בִיהוָה עֲזָרָם וּמְגִנָּתָם הוּא : 11 יִרְאֵי יְהוָה בָּטְחוּ בִיהוָה עֲזָרָם וּמְגִנָּתָם הוּא : 12 יְהוָה זָכְרֵנוּ יְבָרֵךְ יְבָרֵךְ אֶת-בַּיִת יִשְׂרָאֵל יְבָרֵךְ אֶת-בַּיִת אֲהָרֹן : 13 יְבָרֵךְ יִרְאֵי יְהוָה הַקְּטָנִים עִם- הַגְּדֹלִים : 14 יִסַּךְ יְהוָה עֲלֵיכֶם עֲלֵיכֶם וְעַל-בְּנֵיכֶם : 15 בְּרוּכִים אַתֶּם לִיהוָה עֲשֵׂה שָׁמַיִם וָאָרֶץ : 16 הַשָּׁמַיִם שָׁמַיִם לִיהוָה וְהָאָרֶץ נָתַן לְבְנֵי-אָדָם : 17 לֹא הִמְתִּים יְהִלְלוּ-</p>
<p>Psa. 115:9 O "Israel, ^btrust in the LORD; He is their ¹help and their shield. ¹⁰ O house of "Aaron, trust in the LORD; He is their help and their shield.</p>	<p>יִסַּךְ יְהוָה עֲלֵיכֶם עֲלֵיכֶם וְעַל-בְּנֵיכֶם : 15 בְּרוּכִים אַתֶּם לִיהוָה עֲשֵׂה שָׁמַיִם וָאָרֶץ : 16 הַשָּׁמַיִם שָׁמַיִם לִיהוָה וְהָאָרֶץ נָתַן לְבְנֵי-אָדָם : 17 לֹא הִמְתִּים יְהִלְלוּ-</p>

¹¹ You who ^{1a}fear the LORD, trust
 in the LORD;
 He is their help and their shield.
¹² The LORD ^ahas been mindful of
 us; He will bless *us*;
 He will bless the house of Israel;
 He will bless the house of Aaron.
¹³ He will ^abless those who ¹fear the
 LORD,
^bThe small together with the great.
¹⁴ May the LORD ^agive you
 increase,
 You and your children.
¹⁵ May you be blessed of the LORD,
^aMaker of heaven and earth.

Psa. 115:16 The heavens are ^athe
 heavens of the LORD,
 But ^bthe earth He has given to the
 sons of men.
¹⁷ The ^adead do not praise ¹the
 LORD,
 Nor *do* any who go down into
^bsilence;
¹⁸ But as for us, we will ^abless ¹the
 LORD
 From this time forth and forever.
²Praise ¹the LORD!

יְהוָה אֱלֹהֵינוּ כָּל-יְרֵכֵי הַדּוֹמָה : וַאֲנַחְנוּ
 אֲנִיכֶרְךָ יְהוָה מֵעַתָּה וְעַד-עוֹלָם
 תְּהַלְלֶנּוּ :

References

Psalm 115:1

¹Or *faithfulness*

^aIs 48:11; Ezek 36:22

^bPs 29:2; 96:8

Psalm 115:2

^aPs 79:10

^bPs 42:3, 10

Psalm 115:3

^aPs 103:19

^bPs 135:6; Dan 4:35

Psalm 115:4

^aPs 115:4-8; 135:15-18; Jer 10:4

^bDeut 4:28; 2 Kin 19:18; Is 37:19; 44:10, 20; Jer 10:3

Psalm 115:5

^aJer 10:5

Psalm 115:7

¹Lit *Their hands*

²Lit *Their feet*

Psalm 115:8

¹Or *are like them*

^aPs 135:18; Is 44:9-11

Psalm 115:9

^aPs 118:2; 135:19

^bPs 37:3; 62:8

^cPs 33:20

Psalm 115:10

^aPs 118:3; 135:19

Psalm 115:11

¹Or *revere*

^aPs 22:23; 103:11; 135:20

Psalm 115:12

^aPs 98:3

Psalm 115:13

¹Or *revere*

^aPs 103:11; 112:1; 128:1

^bRev 11:18; 19:5

Psalm 115:14

^aDeut 1:11

Psalm 115:15

^aGen 1:1; Neh 9:6; Ps 96:5; 102:25; 121:2; 124:8; 134:3; 146:6; Acts 14:15; Rev 14:7

Psalm 115:16

^aPs 89:11

^bPs 8:6

Psalm 115:17

¹Heb *YAH*

^aPs 6:5; 88:10-12; Is 38:18

^bPs 31:17

Psalm 115:18

¹Heb *YAH*

²Or *Hallelujah!*

^aPs 113:2; Dan 2:20

Targum

Psa. 115:1 Not on our account, O LORD, not on account of our merits, but rather to your name give glory, because of your goodness and because of your truth. ² Why will the Gentiles say, “Where now is their God?” ³ And our God’s residence is in heaven, all that he desires he has done. ⁴ Their idols are of silver and gold, the handiwork of a son of man. ⁵ They have a mouth, but do not speak; they have eyes, and do not see. ⁶ They have ears, and do not hear; they have nostrils, but do not smell. ⁷ Hands, but do not feel; feet, but do not walk; they do not murmur with their throat. ⁸ May their makers become like them, everyone who relies upon them. ⁹ O Israel, trust in the word of the LORD; he is their helper and their shield. ¹⁰ Those of the house of Aaron, trust in the word of the LORD; he is their helper and their shield. ¹¹ You who fear the LORD, trust in the word of the LORD; he is their helper and their shield. ¹² The word of the LORD has remembered us for good, he will bless; he will bless the house of Israel, he will bless the house of Aaron. ¹³ He will bless those who fear the LORD, the small with the great. ¹⁴ The word of the LORD will add to you; to you, and to your sons. ¹⁵ Blessed are you in the presence of the LORD, maker of heaven and earth. ¹⁶ The heavens of the heavens are for the glorious presence of the LORD, and the earth he has given to the sons of men. ¹⁷ The dead do not praise the name of the LORD, nor any of those who go down to the grave of earth. ¹⁸ But we will bless Yah, from now and forevermore. Hallelujah!

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

This Psalm speaks to the long-term effects of the LORD's miracles on the Red Sea and Mount Sinai. These events left an indelible mark of faith on the Jewish people that will last until the end of time. The Gentiles of these events were impressed with the LORD but overtime they forgot about these events. The LORD seems to have left human events to unfold by themselves. The Jewish people beseech the LORD to intervene again not only for Yisrael's sake but also for the LORD's name. The Gentiles need to see something from the LORD which will convince them to worship the LORD and to hold Yisrael as sacred.

Verse one

The people call for the loving-kindness of the Sefirah Chesed which will show to the Gentile nations that the LORD is watching events on Earth and will react.

Not to us, O LORD, not to us, but to Your Name give honor, send the loving-kindness from the Sefirah Chesed which demonstrates Your truth.

Verse ten

Yisrael is called to have trust and faith in the LORD. The House of Aaron were the priests. The priests were the people who interpreted Scripture and led the people in worship to the LORD. Therefore, it was imperative from the priests to have the "strongest" faith in the LORD.

O House of Aharon, trust in the LORD for He is their held and their shield.

Notes on the Psalm

The Psalmist says that even though it is difficult to be a Jew, it is imperative to maintain faith and trust in the LORD. It is difficult to trust the LORD when the persecutions from the Gentile nations occur. The Jews are scattered in various countries around the globe. In many countries, they are persecuted for their religious beliefs. The Torah can be a burden, but the rewards will be there. The rewards may not be seen in this life, but certainly will be shown in the world to come.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

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